

THE DEFORMATION MECHANISM AND DISLOCATION STRUCTURE OF
TiB₂/NiAl COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Dislocation structures in 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composites have been thoroughly investigated with a 1 MeV HVEM after compression testing at 760-1000° C. Samples with 0 and 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl additions have almost identical dislocation structures which can be described as a <100> screw dislocations with extensive jogs and superjogs. Prismatic punched dislocations were observed in all of the deformed composites and deformed samples of 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl had extensive dislocation generation around the particles. Dislocation density, grain size, and the tendency for dislocation reactions or networks forming during deformation decrease as the volume fraction of TiB₂ increases. Also, since a predominance of screw dislocation was observed, the rate controlling process is not likely to be dislocation annihilation or climb, but dislocation generation. The grain size refinement could play an important role in the strengthening of the composites.

KEYWORDS: Microscopy, Particulate composite, Deformation, Dislocation structure, Elevated temperature strength

1. INTRODUCTION

Since a threefold increase of the high temperature strength of TiB₂/NiAl composite has been obtained by the XD™ process [1,2], NiAl has become a plausible matrix material for high temperature composites. However, the reinforcements used in TiB₂/NiAl composites are TiB₂ particulates which are about 2 μm in size. This means that the strengthening cannot be explained by either classical composite mechanics, such as Eshelby's model, or with conventional dislocation theories related to the dispersion hardening. These models predict strengthening rates which are much lower than that of experimental results [3]. The purpose of this work is to thoroughly

characterize the microstructures of TiB_2/NiAl composites before and after deformation at elevated temperatures, and the stability of the microstructure at elevated temperatures. Also, to investigate the dislocation structures of high temperature deformed composites which, in turn, will provide us with some insight to the strengthening mechanism of this composite.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The composites containing 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2 particulates used in this investigation were purchased from the Martin Marietta Co. After hot extrusion, samples were ground to a cylinder with a height to diameter ratio of 2 for compression tests. A series of compression tests at 760, 870, and 1000° C have been carried out at a strain rate range from 10^{-6} to 10^{-2} sec^{-1} . The apparent activation energies of the composites were obtained from the logarithmic plots of the strain rate versus stress data of the compression tests. Then, the samples were cut for TEM studies. Details for TEM sample

preparation can be found in Ref. [3]. Most of the TEM work has been done on the 1 MeV HVEM at Argonne National Laboratory since a foil thickness of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ which is similar to the particle size can be viewed under the 1 MeV microscope.

Fig. 1 Compression stress-strain rate relations of 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl composites at temperature range from 760 - 1000° C.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compression test results of 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl composites are shown in Fig. 1. All the data can be fit in a power law equation, $\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n \exp(-Q/kT)$ where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, σ is the stress, Q , the apparent activation energy, k , the

Boltzmann constant, T , the absolute temperature, and n , the stress exponent. As the volume fraction of TiB_2 increases or the temperature decreases, the value will increase. Since the typical value of the activation energy for self-diffusion of NiAl is $\sim 50\text{-}70$ Kcal/mol [4], the apparent activation energies of deformation as shown in Table 1 are considerably higher than that of self-diffusion of NiAl, especially for those composites which contain higher volume fractions of TiB_2 particles. In comparison with that of 0 and 10 V% TiB_2/NiAl composites, the apparent activation energy of the 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl composite was a function of temperature within the testing temperature range. The apparent activation energy of deformation is a function of stress for all the 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl composites. TEM investigations indicate that as the volume fraction of TiB_2 increases, the grain size decreases. As shown in Fig. 2, particles in 0 V% TiB_2/NiAl are $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and particles in 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl are both TiB_2 and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. Most of the smaller particles in 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl samples are $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. Particles of Al_2O_3 appeared in those samples which can be as high as 5 - 10 V% in all of the composites, including 10 and 20 V% composites. The measured dislocation density of deformed 0 V% TiB_2/NiAl is $\sim 10^{13}\text{ m}^{-2}$. As the volume fraction of TiB_2 increases, the dislocation density decreases. The grain size and particle size, including that of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, remain constant throughout the whole deformation process independent of the testing temperature and strain rate. The bond between the particles (both TiB_2 and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) is excellent [5]. Fiber texture of $\langle 111 \rangle$ type introduced by extrusion exist in all the composites investigated. Edge dislocation segments, edge dipoles and dislocation loops, as shown in Fig. 3, are commonly observed in 0 V% and 10 V% TiB_2/NiAl composites for samples cut from the plane perpendicular to the loading axis which are close to $\{111\}$ planes. For those cut at 45° to the loading axis, long screw axis, long screw dislocations (Fig. 4), or zigzag-shaped dislocations (Fig. 5) are frequently observed as long as the foil plane is close to or between $\{001\}$ or $\{011\}$. This implies that the basic dislocation morphologies are screw dislocations with jogs or superjogs and zigzag-shaped dislocations on a

TABLE 1

Apparent Activation Energies for 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl Composites *

Composites	Apparent Activation Energy Kcal/mol	Remarks
0 V% TiB_2/NiAl	82 ± 2	760-1000° C
10 V% TiB_2/NiAl	87 ± 2	760-1000° C
20 V% TiB_2/NiAl	110 ± 2	870-1000° C
	91 ± 4	760-870° C

* Data obtained are the average values within a stress variation of 20 MPa.

Fig. 2 TEM micrographs of 0 and 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl , (a) 0 V% TiB_2/NiAl particles are $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and (b) 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl .

Fig. 3 TEM micrograph of deformed 0 V% TiB₂/NiAl, edge dislocations, dipoles, and dislocation loops, foil normal parallel to the loading axis.

Fig. 4 TEM micrograph of deformed 0 V% TiB₂/NiAl, long screw dislocation and local deformation around particles. Foil normal is 45° away from the loading axis.

Fig. 5 TEM micrograph of deformed 0 V% TiB_2/NiAl , zigzag-shaped dislocation. Foil normal is 45° away from the loading axis.

Fig. 6 Schematic illustration of screw dislocation with jogs, and effect of sample cuttings.

series of parallel slip planes, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 6. Therefore, the rate controlling type of dislocation is screw, and the dislocation motion is not likely to be controlled by dislocation climb or annihilation. Prismaticly punched dislocations via the particles, including α -Al₂O₃, was observed as a result of the relaxation of stress concentration at the particle-matrix interface, as shown in Fig. 7, which is a TEM micrograph taken from 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl deformed sample. Obviously, this local deformation around the particles does not directly contribute to the overall deformation (Also see Fig. 4), since the grain size is much larger than the particle size. However, the local relaxation of the constrain will certainly introduce a softening effect [6] and, in turn, determine the overall deformation behavior, especially for those composites containing higher volume fractions of reinforcements. Actually, for a 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite, the grain size is greatly reduced to such an extent that the grain size is comparable to the particle size. Extensive dislocation generation both into the matrix and inside the particles themselves was observed [3,7], especially at a higher stress level, as shown in Fig. 8. At the same time, the tendency for dislocation reactions and the formation of networks, which is the case of 0 V% TiB₂/NiAl [3] were greatly decreased. Accordingly, the changes of the activation energies as a function of temperature of 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite also indicated that the deformation mechanism of this composite is different from that of the 0 and 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl composites.

For a 20 V% sample in areas where the local volume fraction of particles is lower than the average volume fraction and the grain size is larger than the average grain size, a dislocation structure which was present in the 0 or 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl was also observed. As shown in Fig. 9, which is a TEM micrograph taken of a deformed 20 V% sample, stereo pairs of TEM micrographs of this area verified that these dislocations are screw dislocations on a series of parallel slip planes with jogs and superjogs. For a 10 V% sample in the areas where the local volume fraction of particles is higher than the average volume fraction and where the grain size is smaller than the average grain size, a dislocation structure which was present in the 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite was observed in the 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite as well. As shown in Fig. 10, which is a TEM micrograph taken of a deformed 10 V% sample, extensively prismaticly punched dislocations were observed. These observations strongly suggested that the dislocation structures were controlled by microstructures of the composites, or to put it more explicitly, controlled by particle concentration and matrix grain size of the composite. There are a number of investigations which show that the strength of NiAl [8-11] and FeAl [12-14] at elevated temperatures can be improved by decreasing the grain size. An empirical equation was obtained from the FeAl experimental data by Whittenberger [14] who expressed the flow stress, σ_f , as a function of grain size, d , in terms of $\sigma_f \propto 1/d^{1/2}$. Since the grain size of 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite has been reduced about five times in comparison with that of 0 V% TiB₂/NiAl composite, a

Fig. 7 TEM micrograph of deformed 10 V% TiB_2/NiAl , prismatic punched dislocations.

Fig. 8 TEM micrograph of deformed 20 V% TiB_2/NiAl . Extensive dislocation generation around and inside particles.

Fig. 9 TEM micrograph of deformed 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl. Screw dislocation with jogs at a area with fewer particles.

Fig. 10 TEM micrograph of deformed 10 V% TiB₂/NiAl. Extensive dislocation generation from particles at a area concentrated with particles.

factor of 2 or more increase of strength could be expected, according to this formula. Usually fine-grained metals and alloys will have less elevated temperature strength than that with larger grain size since the grain boundary sliding will certainly introduce a softening effect. However, for the composites discussed here, grain boundary sliding has been effectively stopped by a large number of thermally stable particles, such as TiB_2 and Al_2O_3 ; instead of introducing the softening effect, grain refinement may be accounting for the strengthening. Actually, the reinforcement does more than just stabilize grain size and prevent the grain boundaries from sliding. Since the local deformation via dislocation generation around the particle was observed in all of the 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2 /NiAl composites, the constraint effect was relaxed to some extent during the deformation process. A simple diffusional process around the particles is obviously not fast enough to relax the stress concentration around the particles. The relaxation rate of this constraint effect would probably control the overall deformation rate.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the above experimental results and analyses, the following conclusions could be arrived at.

- 4.1 The stress exponent, n , and the apparent activation energies for deformation of TiB_2 /NiAl are functions of stress, and volume fractions of the reinforcements. These apparent activation energies are considerably higher than that for self diffusion of NiAl.
- 4.2 As the volume fraction of reinforcement increases, the grain size and dislocation density decrease. The dislocation density of the deformed sample is independent of the stress level.
- 4.3 Basic dislocation morphologies of deformed 0 and 10 V% TiB_2 /NiAl composites are screw dislocations with jogs or superjogs, and zigzag-shaped dislocations on a series of parallel slip planes.
- 4.4 Prismatic punched dislocation were observed for all of the 0, 10, and 20 V% TiB_2 /NiAl composites around the particles. Extensive dislocation generation was observed for 20 V% TiB_2 /NiAl samples, and
- 4.5 Grain size refinement and constraint effect of the reinforcement could play important roles in strengthening of the composites and controlling the rate process.

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7. BIOGRAPHIES

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